

IN-HABIT - INclusive Health And wellBeing In small and medium size ciTies

ACTIVITY GUIDE Co-creating Palmeras with Design for Change (DFC)

Overview:

Guide for high school students to carry out social innovation projects through the DFC Methodology.

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ACTIVITY Co-creating Palmeras:

The goal of this activity is to give you, the young people of Cordoba, the opportunity to be part of the IN-HABIT project by either making the actions being carried out visible or identifying new aspects that can be accomplished in the neighborhood of Las Palmeras.

INHABIT

Brief introduction of the INHABIT project in Cordoba

DESIGN FOR CHANGE

Design for Change (DFC) is an opportunity for young people to put into action their ideas to change their world, beginning with their concerns until they say “I can”, in other words, until they empower themselves.

The work process uses the DFC methodology, which is so simple that anybody can use it. During the process of working with DFC, all the people involved develop their abilities: empathy, creativity, teamwork, critical thinking, and shared leadership. Hence, **it is an opportunity to gain confidence and empathy.**

Design for Change is carried out from the “We Can” perspective, by taking an essential part of a project in which observation, listening, respect and teamwork are crucial. In this way, every young person including you feels the “I Can”; you become empowered, and you become the change you want to see in the world, which is, **through an experimental process.**

When working with DFC, abilities such as uncertainty management or problem-solving are developed without jumping directly to find the solution, favoring the appearance of leaders with

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different profiles depending on each stage of the process, therefore in a different and enriching way.

You, the young people, are the protagonists, therefore you must take responsibility for your own learning, and your engagement with the community is encouraged, with the collaboration of everyone.

Every young person has the opportunity to contribute a particular grain of sand. All topics are covered and, given the global nature of the movement, diversity and multiculturalism are encouraged as well.

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1. What are the keys to developing this activity?

Trust the process

We have the tendency of solving problems in a linear way, passing directly from the problem to the solution. The philosophy on which DFC is based includes elements that require both convergence and divergence, as in the case of creativity. We diversify to increase the range of available options and then concur to choose the best ones.

Expanding the range of possible options increases uncertainty as well, and it can be uncomfortable because it might feel like a kind of "fog" in which it is natural to believe that we are lost or that we are not on the right course. Even if it seems surprising, this is precisely the sign of being on the right course.

We propose working in groups of 4 to 6 members for this activity.

Empathy

It is necessary to be capable of viewing things from other people's perspective. This will help you to get a better understanding of reality. The first step to empathizing is through listening.

Encourage collaboration

Working in a team is exciting and empowering: any team is stronger than a single person on its own. However, it is not always that easy. You must be able to agree and to make decisions that are pleasing to everybody. This, of course, involves accepting compromises. We must be generous both in proposing and accepting the suggestions of others.

Listening as a basis

It is necessary to listen to others and consider their opinions and ideas equally valid as your own opinion, even if you disagree.

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Listen to each other with attention and explain your way of perceiving things. This is how you will feel being part of a greater matter and that the important thing is not that your ideas are implemented, but those of the team, and even those of the whole group.

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2. Work process

2.1. Development in five steps

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Each step is divided into several stages.

	<p>What do you think is relevant to the challenge? Organize the information Identify the focal points Choose a focal point Gain in understanding* Synthesize what you have learned* Specify the challenge</p>	<p>In this step you must investigate to understand the environment that surrounds the challenge. It is based on empathy and understanding. * Optional for this activity</p>
	<p>Propose many ideas Choose the best solutions Make a prototype Specify your proposal*</p>	<p>It includes the creation and elaboration of ideas to improve the situations which have been analyzed in the previous step, and the preparation to put them into practice. * Optional for this activity</p>
	<p>Individual action plan Possible realization</p>	<p>For this activity, the created idea is presented so that the proposals for change can be carried out.</p>
	<p>Reflect on what you have learned</p>	<p>We can apply what we have learned to any other situation that comes our way.</p>
	<p>Share your idea with others</p>	<p>Share your solution with the world.</p>

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2.2. FEEL

TO FEEL, IT IS NECESSARY TO PERCEIVE, INTERPRET AND UNDERSTAND THE WORLD IN WHICH WE LIVE.

In the first step of the process, you will identify the aspects to work on, based on the information provided to you,

In the FEEL step, knowledge about the problem and its environment is being improved, through observation, listening, and analyzing.

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2.2.0 Connecting with the Challenge

Here you can find a video that explains the context and what we are seeking to achieve with this activity.

2.2.1 What do you think is relevant about this challenge?

Even though it would be ideal to understand the people for what you are creating and their background, on this occasion we are going to stick with the information provided in the video. After an individual reflection, write down everything that seems relevant to you and note each observation on a Post-it. Then you read what you have written and place it on the large paper that belongs to the entire group, without organizing it beforehand. This is the moment to find “facts” and not “ideas”. Postpone the search for solutions to the IMAGINE step.

Materials: Post-it notes, markers, flip chart sheet, or something equivalent.

2.2.2 Organize the information

At this point, you will be looking at a large number of unorganized Post-it notes. Arrange them by putting together the observations that, in your opinion, are related to each other, and explain why. It is a good time to have conversations.

At the end, you will find all the observations grouped in “clouds of information”, based on the group's criteria.

2.2.3 Identify the focal points

Each “cloud” reflects a set of situations that can be improved in some way. Express briefly what is included in the cloud. It is very useful to describe it in a sentence with subject and predicate. It will help you to test several possibilities. It may also be helpful to make some kind of drawing so that we can express what we are talking about.

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When you have identified a sentence that summarizes a cloud, write it next to it. It is important not to remain on the surface and try to go into more detail.

Materials: Markers in several colors

2.2.4 Choose a focal point

Once the potential focal points for the solution development have been identified, it is important to choose which one(s) to work on. A two-step voting system helps to make a better selection. Vote for the two or three problems that you consider most relevant. Choose the most voted ones and make a second vote, this time with only one single vote per person.

2.2.5 Gain in understanding (optional)

This stage is optional, you may want to get more information about the focus you have selected, if so, you can contact the INHABIT project managers in Cordoba at the following email address spain@dfcworld.com (Include Co-creating Palmeras in the subject line)

When talking with them keep in mind:

Who do you think the situation may affect?

Talk to them to find out how they experience it. It is not a matter of finding out if they agree with what you have thought but finding out what they think about the subject in question. It is better to ask open questions that lead to conversations; this way you will be able to hear anecdotes and experiences, avoiding questions whose answer is only yes or no.

Write down everything that catches your attention, without missing anything, documenting the research as well as possible (drawings, photographs, videos, etc.). If you take photos or videos, you have to ask for permission first.

Materials: Guidelines for the interview

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2.2.6 Synthesize what you have learned (optional)

Only do this stage if you have done the previous one. Synthesize everything you know, explaining the following:

What the situation consists of

What the situation consists of

You have likely built a new interpretation based on what you have learned so that the focus of your work has developed. In this case, rephrase the sentence that initially expressed what was inside the cloud, to reflect the focus as you understand it at the moment, and write it in a large font on a new sheet of paper.

Who is affected and how it affects them

Their thoughts, feelings, and actions about the problem. Remember that the more clearly and visually it is expressed, the better.

2.2.7 Specify the challenge

For this you can use the formula How shall we...? in the following ways:

How could we... *[increase, reduce, improve, change, optimize, eliminate, create, achieve]* that ... *[users]* solve the... *[need]* in... *[setting]*?

For example: How could we *get older people to take advantage of technology for their celebrations during lockdown?*

Create several challenges and choose the one you find most engaging and motivating.

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2.3. IMAGINE

LET YOUR IMAGINATION BE THE FIRST STEP TO BUILD A NEW REALITY

In this phase think of ways to solve the problem you have been looking into.

The IMAGINE step is a creative and collaborative stage in which a variety of unexpected abilities arise.

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2.3.1 Propose many ideas

The best way to find good ideas is to create many. Use your imagination, and come up with daring, outrageous, and fantastic ideas; without judging any proposal and building on the ideas of others. You can take an idea that has been expressed and divide it into two, exaggerate it, transform it, and combine it with others. It is essential to listen to each other: respect each other's turn to speak and try to express yourself in a simple and clear way.

At the beginning of a brainstorming session, first some proposals emerge slowly (it drizzles), then many emerge (it rains!) and finally, it drizzles again. Be patient and confident: Ideas will come up!

Materials: Flip chart sheet or something equivalent and markers in several colors.

2.3.2 Choose the best solutions

Considering these possible ideas, select which one(s) you will implement. Vote individually for the proposals that you like the best and that interest and attract you the most. 1 or 2 votes per person is enough, though it depends on how many ideas have come up. Choose the most voted ideas and discuss them, imagining which ones can best help to solve the problem.

After that, make a second vote using one vote per person.

2.3.3 Make a prototype

A prototype is a “first example” of an idea, a step towards turning it into reality. Creating prototypes is very useful to gain a better understanding of each person's vision of an idea, and it also helps to define better what it is that you want to do.

For this activity, we suggest you make a drawing that will allow you to explain your idea.

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Explain your prototype to another group that will give you feedback with the following approach: “What we found most interesting is... and in addition, you could...” to which you can only reply: **thank you!**

Afterwards, the other group presents their prototype to you, and you give them feedback using the same approach.

2.3.4 Specify your idea

What the idea consists of

A short sentence that summarizes the proposal.

Who is it going to help?

Which individuals will benefit from the solution?

What will it be useful for?

What do you want to achieve once it is implemented?

What is necessary to carry it out?

Both material resources and the collaboration of other people that do not belong to the group are required.

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IMAGINE

Specify your proposal Co-creating Palmeras

Challenge

What the idea consists of

Who is it going to help?

What will it be useful for?

What is necessary to carry it out?

Prototype

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2.4. DO

THE MOST VALUABLE LESSONS BEGIN IN REAL ACTIONS FOR CHANGE

In this step, we usually take action in the real world, but for this activity, your idea may remain "just" a proposal, nevertheless, we invite you to consider individually which aspect of it you can implement, even if it is on a small scale.

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2.4.1 Take action

We propose 2 activities:

Send your proposal to the INHABIT team by sending an e-mail to spain@dfcworld.com

Among all the proposals that have been submitted, the representatives of the INHABIT project, in collaboration with representatives of the neighborhood, will choose the actions they consider most interesting:

- They choose those that will be implemented with the support of the students who have proposed them.
- Visibility will be given through the social networks of the project itself.

Individual Action Plan

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You can download this sheet from the same link you downloaded the guide.

2.5. EVOLUATE

REFLECTING ON OUR ACTIONS HELPS US TO GROW

For this activity, we are going to focus on apprenticeships in this phase.

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The EVOLUATE step combines development and evaluation, in which the goal is to look into the future and to imagine new actions that can benefit the work that has been carried out.

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2.5.1 Reflect on the activity

Whether your idea has been implemented or has remained on an action plan, you will certainly learn a lot from the process you have gone through. Share them among the group members and then with the rest of the class.

2.5.2 Make your solution evolve

If your idea has been selected and implemented, we invite you to use this evaluation tool:

Start / Stop / Continue

Reach a group consensus on three points. First, something that has not been done during the process and that you would like to have been able to do (START); second, something that has been done and that you consider must stop (STOP); finally, something that has been done and that is worth keeping on doing (CONTINUE). Write each aspect in three panels, each belonging to one section (START/STOP/CONTINUE). Afterward, read them aloud and discuss them with the whole group.

Remember that the solutions can be improved, and that you can carry out the work process as many times as you consider necessary. Skill comes from practice, so the more you do it, the better results you will get.

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2.6. SHARE

SHARE THE EXPERIENCES WE LIVE BUILD OUR HISTORY

Share your experiences on social networks with #CocreandoPalmeras

The SHARE step is a way to highlight the value of what you have done. It is worth being shared and it can inspire others. The goal is that your solution can be used by as many people as possible.

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2.6.1 Share your solution

You have the opportunity to use your creativity to let us know how you want to share with the world the solution you have come up with, use the #CocreandoPalmeras and send us your proposal through the following [form](#).

2.6.2 Spread your solution

It's time to tell the world what you have done!

If your idea is selected, the INHABIT team will make your solution visible through the social network of the project. Stay tuned to give it the maximum diffusion.

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ANNEXES

Scheduling to be done in 1.5 hours (2 consecutive sessions)

Phase/Activity	Time
FEEL 2.2.0 Connecting with the Challenge 2.2.1 What do you think is relevant to the challenge? 2.2.2 Organize the information 2.2.3 Identify the focal points 2.2.4 Choose a focal point 2.2.5 Gain in understanding (optional) 2.2.6 Synthesize what you have learned (optional) 2.2.7 Specify the challenge	(45 min. + 70 min. optional) 5 min. 15 min. 5 min. 10 min. 5 min. 60 min. 10 min. 5 min.
IMAGINE 2.3.1 Propose many ideas 2.3.2 Choose the best solutions 2.3.3 Make a prototype 2.3.4 Specify your idea	(35 min.) 10 min. 5 min. 10 min. 10 min.
DO 2.4.1 Take action	(5 min.) 5 min.
EVOLUATE 2.5.1 Reflect on the activity 2.5.2 Evolve your solution* * Optional	(5 min. +20 min. optional) 5 min. 20 min.
SHARE	(20 min.) after the session

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2.6.1 Share your solution	10 min.
2.6.2 Spread your solution	10 min.

Schedule to do it in 2 sessions of 45 min (2 separate sessions)

First session

Phase/Activity	Time
FEEL	(45 min. + 70 min. optional)
2.2.0 Connecting with the Challenge	5 min.
2.2.1 What do you think is relevant to the challenge?	15 min.
2.2.2 Organize the information	5 min.
2.2.3 Identify the focal points	10 min.
2.2.4 Choose a focal point	5 min.
2.2.5 Gain in understanding (optional)	60 min.
2.2.6 Synthesize what you have learned (optional)	10 min.
2.2.7 Specify the challenge	5 min.

Second session

Phase/activity	Time
Reconnecting with the previous session First, each group shares the point where they left it in the previous session.	(5 min.)
IMAGINE 2.3.1 Propose many ideas	(35 min.) 10 min.

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2.3.2 Choose the best solutions 2.3.3 Make a prototype 2.3.4 Specify your idea	5 min. 10 min. 10 min.
DO 2.4.1 Take action	(5 min.) 5 min.
EVALUATE 2.5.1 Reflect on the activity 2.5.2 Evolve your solution* * Optional	(5 min. +20 min. optional) 5 min. 20 min.
SHARE 2.6.1 Share your solution 2.6.2 Spread your solution	(20 min.) after the session 10 min. 10 min.

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